

Curvature Terminators and Conservation of Energy - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, a varying Lorentz manifold with arbitrary variation that vanish into matter, it is possible to predict that conservation of energy will not hold. That is because new matter is being created in accordance to the arrow of time. The one exception and the only way to ensure the conservation of energy, is to present an additional set of terminators, i.e. anti-matter. Nature is eliminating the arbitrary amount of curvature in two stages; first, it creates matter as was presented in the 8T thesis. However, to ensure the conservation of energy it has another stage of elimination, which is complete elimination and that is anti-matter.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. In the 8T thesis, we have derived the arbitrary variation term (1.48) which we inserted on equation (1) to describe fermions.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

Discretizing and partitioning the term δg into a series of sub elements, we derived the existence of fermions, i.e. showing that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements. The original proof in the 8T thesis is presented here as well. Given four elements distinct:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 > 0$$

$$\delta g_3 + \delta g_4 < 0$$

If

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 + \delta g_4 \neq 0$$

Than the overall series cannot vanish, by that logic we need even amounts of equal elements of pluses and minuses. The amount must be even and summed as zero, ensuring stationary Lorentz manifold. Suppose that we had three distinct elements, two pluses and minus:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 > 0$$

or

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_3 < 0$$

Demanding the series to vanish this will exclude this result, and so there could not be three distinct elements in the series, else the overall series will not vanish to zero. As a result of those sceneries, we require the series to have an even amount of variation elements, manifesting as two distinct elements in the series, which differ in sign. If we allow those sub elements in the series to vary as well, and by the above reasoning, there are only two elements in the series, they are varying in a discrete way, or forming a group. Let it be only four elements in the series and one of the pluses just changed its nature

$$\mathbf{0}: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination. $\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$ For example. Even though the sub elements in the series are varying, the overall series can vanish. Now, count all the ways of possible combinations of those elements. We are going to analyze by the integral signs. Since it is a group, there is a natural map, which change an element to itself. One built his analysis firstly on those natural maps. So:

$$(1(e)1(e)1)$$

$$2(e)2(e)2$$

$$(221)$$

$$(112)$$

$$(211)$$

$$(122)$$

$$(212)$$

$$(121)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T Thesis fundamentals presented in pages 3 – 5. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. The main point of this proof, which was only briefly mentioned, is that nature is aspiring to eliminate the curvature. The result of the elimination is yielding the group that allowed physicists to predict the existence of the omega minus (333) in the 8T. However even if (1.48) is vanishing to zero, there is constant creation of matter. Arbitrary variation of the manifold are not obeying a time limit, they can and are created in a random fashion. So one way to put it is that **energy is not conserved**. That is because matter is constantly being created, and matter is synonymous with energy.

The only way to ensure that the energy will be conserved is to present a new way of curvature terminators that is anti-matter. We allow the existence of anti-matter as the coupling magnitudes are preserved under sign reversal.

$$\left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \left[-2N_3 - \frac{1}{2}\right] - \frac{1}{2} \quad (1.45)$$

We analyzed the subject of anti-matter in previous paper, and in particular the subject of orthogonal curvature, which has inner product zero. So to ensure the conservation of energy, we will have to present the set of arbitrary curvature terminators, for fermions, it has two inverse elements.

$$X = [-\delta g_1, +\delta g_2]$$

$$\langle \delta g_i | -\delta g_i \rangle = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

So overall, there are two main stages of curvature elimination. First arbitrary variation vanish into matter, as presented in the 8T thesis and the prove above. Secondly, to ensure the conservation of energy, anti-matter terminators are presented. Whether energy is actually conserved is unknown, author tend to belief is not. That is due to the asymmetry of matter to anti-matter in the universe. If for each matter created there is also an anti-matter particle, anti-matter should be more common. We have presented the same procedure of orthogonal curvatures to leptons and Bosons. We used equation (1.46) with leptons as elements of the inner product such as the electron and positron:

$$\langle +3_i | -3_i \rangle = 0$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Same rules apply for the photon as an example:

$$\langle \gamma_i | \gamma_i^- \rangle = 0$$

Summing up, if require the conservation of energy we must present the arbitrary curvature terminators, i.e. Anti-matter. If the number of anti-matter terminators is smaller than the number of arbitrary variations which vanish into matter, which seems to be the case on our manifold, than energy is **not** conserved, as matter is constantly being created.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)